

more

Motivations, experiences and consequences of returns and readmissions policy: revealing and developing effective alternatives

Executive Summary

Alternative policy approaches to RR: regularisation and other recognised statuses

Case Study: **Sweden**

Authors: Aida Ibricevic, Branka Likic-Brboric, Zoran Slavnic

Funded by

Funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Number: 101094107

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by

UK Research
and Innovation

Disclaimer:

This document provides a concise summary of the key findings from the MORE Project WP2 in Sweden. For detailed analysis, evidence, and comprehensive insights, please refer to the full report. The information in this summary should not be considered complete or fully representative of the entire study.

How to Cite:

Ibricevic, A., Slavnic, Z., Likic-Brboric, B. (2025) *Alternative policy approaches to RR: regularisation and other recognised statuses. Case study: Sweden (Executive Summary)*, More Project.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14939163](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14939163)

Publication date:

January 2025

PROJECT COORDINATOR

PARTNERS

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by

UK Research
and Innovation

1. Introduction

This report looks at Swedish legal and policy statuses as they pertain to rejected asylum seekers whose return decisions have impediments to return; the socio-economic rights associated with their return decisions being suspended and the socio-economic rights they gain once their status is regularized through the issuance of a 12-month residence permit; and the practice of “track changes” previously unique to Sweden as a promising alternative to expulsion.

2. Main findings

There is significant dissonance between how policies are formulated, implemented/interpreted by official authorities; and how they are viewed by researchers and activists-at both the policy-making and policy-implementing levels;

- In practice, irregular migrants/asylum seekers are often left in a legal limbo:
 - facing perpetual asylum-seeking processes (Section 2.4);
 - cannot be accepted by their home state unless their return is entirely voluntary (Section 2.9);
 - with the burden of proof placed on themselves, where they have to prove that they have done everything “within their control” to return to the home state, but failed (Section 2.9);
 - at the “mercy” of the Migration Agency and their estimate of the existence of impediments of return that are “beyond the migrant’s control” (Section 2.9);
 - relying on the goodwill of volunteer legal counsellors for any legal aid, while there is no state support for it (Section 2.13).
- There is an observable shift of responsibility for TCNs whose return decisions cannot be enforced from the national to the local, municipal level (Section 3.1).

PROJECT COORDINATOR

PARTNERS

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by

UK Research
and Innovation

3. Recent policy developments

The current system in Sweden has been undergoing a considerable shift away from humanitarian/human rights concerns and legal certainty towards increasing effectiveness/efficiency since 2015/2016. In this context, effectiveness/efficiency refers to increasing the “number and percentage of refusals of entry and expulsions” (Malm Lindberg, 2020, p. 67) relative to issued return decisions.

- A major overhaul of nearly the entire migration and integration policy in Sweden is underway as a result of the Tidö agreement.
- Part of the paradigmatic shift envisioned by the Tidö agreement is a proposal to abolish the “track changes” option as a pathway towards regularization.

4. Alternative promising practices

Some hope can be found at the municipal level, but further research is needed to identify specific municipalities that could be implementing some alternatives to expulsions and the successes/challenges of such local efforts.

PROJECT COORDINATOR

PARTNERS

5. References / Further reading

Civil Rights Defenders. (2023). *Ett år med Tidöavtalet-Det är helheten som oroar/One year with the Tidö agreement-As a whole it is worrying*. Civil Rights Defenders. <https://crd.org/2023/12/12/new-report-as-a-whole-it-is-worrying-one-year-with-the-tido-agreement/>

EMN. (2021). *Responses to long-term irregularly staying migrants: Practices and challenges in the EU and Norway*. European Migration Network.

EMN. (2023a). *Ad-Hoc Query on 2023.11 Procedure for the issuance of residence permits for medical reasons*. European Migration Network.

EMN. (2023b). *Ad-Hoc Query on 2023.34-Access to education and employment for irregularly staying migrants*. European Migration Network.

EMN Sweden. (2017). *The effectiveness of return in EU Member States: Challenges and good practices linked to EU rules and standards-Country Report Sweden*.

EMN Sweden. (2020). *EMN Annual Report on Migration and Asylum 2019—Sweden*.

Malm Lindberg, H. M. (2020). *Those who cannot stay: Implementing return policy in Sweden*. Report 2020:1, Delmi.

Lundberg, A. (2020). "Pushed out in limbo – The every-day decision-making about 'practical impediments to enforcement' in the Swedish management of return migration."

Lundberg, A. (2023). "They Stopped the Lives of Others": Stateless Palestinians Facing Bureaucratic Violence in Sweden. *Refuge: Canada's Journal on Refugees*, 39(2), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.25071/1920-7336.41063>

Lundberg, A., & Kjellbom, P. (2021). Social work law in nexus with migration law. A legal cartographic analysis of inter-legal spaces of inclusion and exclusion in Swedish legislation. *Nordic Social Work Research*, 11(2), 142–154. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2156857X.2020.1861071>

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by

UK Research
and Innovation

SOU, 2017:84. (2017). *Uppehållstillstånd på grund av praktiska verkställighetshinder och preskription. Betänkande av Utredningen om uppehållstillstånd på grund av praktiska verkställighetshinder./Residence permit due to practical obstacles to enforcement and limitation period.*

SOU, 2024:15. (2024). *Nya regler för arbetskraftsinvandring m.m./New rules for labor immigration etc.*

Tidöavtalet: Överenskommelse För Sverige/The Tidö Agreement: Agreement for Sweden.

Utlänningslag (2005:716)/Aliens Act (2005:716). https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-och-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/utlanningslag-2005716_sfs-2005-716/

Wikrén, G., & Sandesjö, H. (2017). *Utlänningslagen med kommentarer (11th ed.)*. Wolders kluwer.

PROJECT COORDINATOR

PARTNERS

